

FROM POLICY TO PROGRESS: HOW VISION 2030 IS SHAPING WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT IN SAUDI ARABIA

BY

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Abstract:

This study explores the transformation of women's empowerment in Saudi Arabia, emphasizing the nation's Vision 2030 as a key determinant. It analyzes how government initiatives have evolved from policy frameworks to tangible progress in social and economic domains. Using a quantitative approach, a five-point Likert scale questionnaire covering six constructs – Policy Support (PS), Personal Empowerment (PE), Economic Empowerment (EE), Social and Cultural Empowerment (SC), Leadership Empowerment (LED), and Economic Development (ED) – was administered. Out of a targeted 180 participants, 141 valid responses were obtained. For the results of the questionnaire SPSS was used as research tool and along with trend analysis some regression model and analysis of variance ANOVA were used. The findings confirm that Vision 2030 has made a considerable difference to strengthening women's participation across multiple sectors and that empowerment policies have socio-economic effects. The research recommends future studies utilizing more advanced statistical tools and comprehensive datasets to deepen understanding and assist policymakers in further refining women empowerment strategies.

Keywords: women empowerment, policy support, leadership empowerment, economical progress, regression analysis, cultural empowerment

I. INTRODUCTION:

Women's empowerment represents the multidimensional process aimed at enhancing women's political, social and economic strength. It entails giving women greater control over their lives and resources, encouraging independence, and promoting gender equality. Global economic engagement by women is critical for long-term economic growth. Despite tremendous progress, barriers such as limited access to education, credit and legal rights remain, especially in poor nations. Addressing these obstacles can help women reach their full prospects, resulting in macroeconomics benefits. (Kabeer, 2021) explains how market mechanism maintain and sustain gender inequities in society, restricting women from contributing to more inclusive forms of economic progress. (Doepke & Tertilt, 2019) highlight that financial control in women's hands, particularly mothers, tends to increase investment in children's education and well-being –

creating long-term intergenerational benefits. Evidence from (Cabeza-García et al., 2019) indicated that financial inclusion, such as access to banking services and credit facilities, directly supports women's economic participation and, consequently, national development. (Blau & Kahn, 2020) further argue that shifts in labor market dynamics and wage structures explain much of the existing gender pay disparities, emphasizing the need for policy reforms that promote equality in economic rewards. Education plays a foundational role in empowerment and sustainable development.

(Tyagi et al., 2021) stress the importance of essential issues of education for sustainable development, such as poverty alleviation, health, environmental protection, human rights, and climate change, into the traditional education system of imparting information and skills required for success in the workplace. (Mathur et al., 2022) undertakes a comprehensive review of Sustainable Development

Goal 4 “Quality Education” and focuses on providing lasting learning opportunities and practical skills through quality Technical and Vocational Education Training (TVET). TVET has immense potential for economic motion and progress, where there is a big working age unemployed population.

(Hyland et al., 2020) shows for the first time the global picture of gender discrimination by the law as it impacts women’s economic opportunities, as well as the progression of legal inequities over five decades. They used the “World Bank’s Women, Business, and the Law Database,” to document huge and persistent gender discrepancies, particularly in terms of salary and parenting treatment.(Feeney & Stritch, 2019) states about family-friendly workplace policies, gender equality, and work-life integration in the public sector and are key mechanisms for supporting women’s career and advancement in public service, as well as improving gender equity in the public sector. They assess the impact of employee take-up leave policies, employer-supported to child care, alternative work scheduling, and a family-supportive culture on Work-Life Balance (WLB).

(Keith et al., 2023) in their review indicated that social empowerment interventions are helpful for changing gender attitudes and norms of lowering Gender-Based Violence (GBV), whereas psychological empowerment interventions are effective for addressing GBV-related symptoms, and their evidence for economic empowerment initiatives was inconclusive. (Alkan et al., 2021) reveal that economic abuse within households- particularly intimate partner violence (IPV) – remains a pressing issue in many societies, requiring both policy and community-level solutions. Corporate and media narratives further shape perceptions of gender equality.

(Sterbenk et al., 2022) investigated the possibility for a new type of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) washing: gender equality through advertising and promotion gender equality known as “femvertisements”. However, it is unclear whether companies that win femvertising awards actually support women through an institutionalized approach to gender equality, no significant differences were found in the number of external efforts or female leadership representation between companies that won femvertisements and those that did not.(Van Der Pas & Aldering, 2020) study about the media coverage

about men and women politicians and finds that, “there is a gender imbalance in the quantity of coverage of politicians in proportional electoral system, with women politicians receiving less media attention than men,” however this gender prejudice is absent in majoritarian voting systems. Overall, women politicians receives more attention for their appearance and personal lives, as well as more negative viability coverage and, to a lesser level, stereotypical issues and trait reporting.

(Irene, 2019) studies about the entrepreneurship that people in the digital age are more enterprising, loyal, open-minded, and less motivated by money than previous generations. Author shows that women are less tech-savvy than men. Techno-preneurship and the impact on technology on women’s entrepreneurship, with the goal of creating a foundation for comprehending the consequences for women’s business strategies in the age of Gen Y and Z.(Sultana & Akter, 2021)demonstrates the role of e-commerce business among women in Bangladesh who have made significant contribution to digital platforms over the last two centuries, and their role as entrepreneurs is inspiring. The further said that Cyber security is now the driving force behind online enterprises, with web users developing trust in the digital world. Finally, everyone in the community must work together to ensure women’s digital access and a safe environment.

(Akhter & Cheng, 2020) explain about the microcredit which is a powerful tool that has been recognized to alleviate poverty, especially in developing countries. Micro credit among poor rural women and sustainable socio-economic development provides novelty to the concept of “sustainability of empowerment.”(Nassani et al., 2019)puts stress on SDG-5 “Gender Equality & Women Empowerment” by contribution of international tourism development by providing equal opportunity to women to sustain their livelihoods such as (i) gender parity in tertiary enrollment, (ii) gender parity in primary and secondary school enrollment, (iii) female employment, and (iv) women share in non-agriculture wage employment. While their results also supports (i) growth-led tourism, (ii) finance-led growth, (iii) growth stimulates women empowerment, and (iv) tourism-induced women’s empowerment hypothesis across countries.

The Gulf region, which includes Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Kuwait, Qatar, Bahrain and Oman, has undergone major economic development in recent decades. Historically reliant on oil earnings, these countries have pursued economic diversification initiatives to promote sustainable development. Policymakers and academics are paying great attention on economic development and women empowerment is one of the most important focus point. There is close link between economic development and women empowerment in the Gulf region and is being reflected in the policy implications with regards to problems and trends. The rapid development of the Gulf region can mostly be attributed to the revenue generated through the sale of oil and it has been used to funding the various infrastructure and social projects. The states in the Gulf are trying hard to reduce their dependence on oil and gas. Within this framework, Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 represents a transformative policy agenda, placing women's empowerment at the heart of its social and economic reforms.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Women empowerment encompasses the capacity of women to make independent decision related to various issues and concerns related to life and to mitigate the risks associated with it to increase their status and well-being. An empowered women is in a position to bring about change in herself and in the society at large which in turn enhances her confidence and self-esteem. Women empowerment leads to the overall development of a nation and it is reflected rightly so in social advancement, improvement in social and mental health and in turn leads to social betterment. No doubt women empowerment plays a very important role in the overall development of a nation and Saudi Arabia being no exception. Keeping this in mind the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has undertaken many initiatives and has made great progress in terms of empowering women and increasing their participation at all levels. The recent efforts in terms of reform and legislation that have been made in line with the Kingdom's Vision 2030 is reflected in the goals of women's empowerment. The Saudi Vision 2030 is very much focused on advancing the UN's Sustainable Development Goal 5, which strives for gender equality. When talking about this Vision, it's crucial to acknowledge the importance of

the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGS) 2030. The majority of nations in the world have adopted these global goals, which shows a shared commitment to enhancing the sustainability of the each and advancing human well-being via national, institutional, and international initiatives for sustainable global growth. The empowerment of Saudi Arabian women is at the heart of the Kingdom's 'Vision 2030' reform program with the stated aim of increasing women participation in the job market from 22 percent to 30 percent (Saleh & Malibari, 2021). According to (Al-Qahtani et al., 2020) women's empowerment is critical in academia for developing educational policies that increases women's capacity. Women's political empowerment is also crucial because it allows them to propose suitable policies, norms and laws that promote women's empowerment in all sectors of the economy and society. Rapid and extensive growth and development have occurred throughout the nation since its inception in 2016 to empower women, changing the social, cultural and economic environment and transforming Saudi Arabia into a more inclusive nation. The Saudi Vision 2030 was launched in 2018 and with regards to women empowerment, the Kingdom has implemented numerous laws and policies to advance this cause. Keeping in line with Saudi Vision 2030, many steps have been taken to facilitate women empowerment. In the year 2018 the first anti-harrassment law was put into place which made provision of safety for women a priority (Alsubaie, 2020). This legislation imposes sever penalties and imprisonment up to five years thus providing women a safer environment in all walks of life. On 24th June 2018 the women in Saudi Arabia were granted the "right to drive" which was a major step with regards to women empowerment and overnight about 2.5 million became eligible to drive. The sped also had a significant economic impact and the auto sales increased yearly by 9% (Wheeler, 2020). In the year 2019, women above the age of 21 were allowed to apply passports and could travel alone not requiring the consent of a male guardian. This was a significant step forward and it provided "Freedom to Travel". In the year 2021 the women were granted the right to make their own living arrangements, not requiring the consent on a male guardian and it guaranteed "The Right to Live Alone" (Rizvi & Hussain, 2022). The "Right to serve in the military",

was granted to the Saudi women in the year 2018. Now the women could serve in the military and other security agencies. This step further enhanced their personal freedom (Ghobain et al., 2024). Women were now encouraged to participate in various sporting activities like football, cycling, horse riding to name a few and with move women now had “Access to Sport” (Alghamdi & Aldossari, 2024). Last but not the least women there guaranteed equal pay at workplace and it too was an important milestone as it provided “Equality in workplace”. With all the positive changes, now the women were in position to start their own businesses and they had a variety of career option to choose from. Over all steps taken by the Kingdom significantly empowered the Saudi women (Al-Nasrallah, 2023).

The Ministry of Human Resources and Social Development (MHRSD) under took several initiatives to provide more jobs to women and in this direction several legislation were put into place to help women enter the workforce. The MHRSD implemented to changes the labor market to provide employment to women. Some examples for the same are the “Qurrah,” “Wusool,” and “Tamheer” programs (Samarin & Al-Asfour, 2023). For working women eighty percent of their transportation expenses are covered by Wusool (Macias-Alonso et al., 2023). Qurrah provides child support for female employees (Almaghlouth & Almujaivel, 2023) and on-the-job training for the female employees is provided by Tamheer (Samarin & Al-Asfour, 2023). As per the recent figures around 1 million Saudi women employed in the private sector i.e., almost half of the Kingdom’s workforce.

Around 17.17 percent of the Saudi women are engaged in Entrepreneurial activities, when compared to Saudi men which is only 17 percent, this is as per the report published by the London-based Global Entrepreneurship Monitor. This is because female entrepreneurship is consistently encouraged through a number of enabling programs (GEM, 2023). Women can now go to public events like concerts and movies. For the first time in history, women are permitted to enter sporting stadiums, allowing women and children to enjoy activities that were previously exclusively for men. This is a component of Vision 2030’s expansion of the sports and entertainment industries. In addition to the Women’s Football League, twenty-two women’s

national teams have been formed (Alghamdi & Aldossari, 2024). According to the minister of sports, this has resulted in a 149% rise in women’s participation in sports (Fakehy et al., 2023). Diversification is the goal of every change being implemented under Vision 2030, and the Kingdom is currently seeing the full impact of these changes. Nowadays, Saudi women are employed in practically every industry, including Finance, FMCG, hospitality, airports, and aviation.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study examines how Saudi Arabia’s Vision 2030 has influenced women’s empowerment, particularly in policy, economic, and leadership domains. The research employed a quantitative approach, using primary data collected through a structured questionnaire designed to capture participants’ perceptions and experiences regarding empowerment initiatives with the Kingdom. While the data with sample size of 180 initially set but after screening 141 valid responses were gathered from the five-point Likert scale with the aim to measure attitude, perceptions and their experience towards the objective of the study. Primary data was acquired through a standardized questionnaire comprised of six constructs: Policy Support (PS), Personal Empowerment (PE), Economic Empowerment (EE), Social and Cultural Empowerment (SC), Leadership Empowerment (LED), and Economic Development (ED) with target questions of each construct that was administered according to a schedule and distributed among target sample size to ensure the reliable survey.

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN

The primary objective of this study is to examine the effectiveness of various experiential and pedagogical learning methodologies in promoting students’ entrepreneurial inclinations. A structured questionnaire served as a primary data collection tool for this quantitative study. The survey was constructed by modifying popular questionnaires from prior studies. In order to ascertain the validity and reliability of the questionnaire a preliminary pilot test was conducted before conducting the main study.

A. Measurement Model

The measurement model of SPSS was used to establish the validity and reliability of the variables (Memon et al., 2021) which establishes the connection between the observed indicators and the latent variables. In order

to ensure meaningful findings from the structural model the indicators must correctly reflect the underlying latent variables. It is important that before trying to establish the relationship between the variables in the structural mode, internal consistency,

convergent validity, and discriminant validity is verified and the measurement models is tool for doing so. This ensures that the constructs are precisely defined and measured, as illustrated in Figure.1 and further explained in (Richter et al., 2016).

B. Data Analysis

Table. 1 Statistics

Statistics					
		GENDER	AGE	EDUCATION	MONTHLY INCOME
N	Valid	141	141	141	141
	Missing	0	0	0	0

Table. 2 Gender

GENDER					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	79	56.0	56.0	56.0
	FEMALE	62	44.0	44.0	100.0
	Total	141	100.0	100.0	

Figure. 1 Gender

Table. 3 Age

AGE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	16 TO 24	35	24.8	24.8	24.8
	25 TO 35	40	28.4	28.4	53.2
	36 TO 50	36	25.5	25.5	78.7
	> 50	30	21.3	21.3	100.0
	Total	141	100.0	100.0	

Figure. 2 Age

**Table. 4 Education
EDUCATION**

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid HIGH SCHOOL OR INTERMEDIATE	30	21.3	21.3	21.3
UNIVERSITY	48	34.0	34.0	55.3
MASTERS	31	22.0	22.0	77.3
DOCTORATE	32	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total	141	100.0	100.0	

Figure. 3 Education
Table. 5 Monthly Income
MONTHLY INCOME

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2000 – 3000	20	14.2	14.2	14.2
	3000 – 4000	28	19.9	19.9	34.0
	4000 – 6000	26	18.4	18.4	52.5
	6000 – 8000	29	20.6	20.6	73.0
	8000 or more	38	27.0	27.0	100.0
	Total		141	100.0	100.0

Table. 6 Model Summary
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.476 ^a	.726	.698	.62914	.226	7.901	5	135	.000	1.653

a. Predictors: (Constant), PE, EE, SC, LED, ED

b. Dependent Variable: PS

Based on the regression model suggest quite moderate prediction of 72.6% of Policy Support (PS) from the predictors PE, EE, SC, LED, ED that are Personal Empowerment, Economic Empowerment, Social and Cultural Empowerment, Leadership Empowerment and Economic Empowerment. Further the value of Durbin-Watson is close to 2 that indicates no serious correlation was found among residuals.

Table. 7 Anova^a
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	15.637	5	3.127	7.901	.000 ^b
	Residual	53.436	135	.396		
	Total	69.073	140			

a. Dependent Variable: PS

b. Predictors: (Constant), PE, EE, SC, LED, ED

Further ANOVA test was conducted to know whether regression model was significant or not. After carefully investigating the results depicted in the

ANOVA table confirms the model fitness of regression table as mentioned above.

V. DISCUSSION

The research's conclusions offers insightful information about how different conceptions contribute to women's empowerment in the context of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030. A thorough investigations of the connections between important factors was made possible by the use of the structured questionnaire and quantitative methods including SPSS, regression analysis and ANOVA. The findings demonstrate the constructs like Personal Empowerment (PE), Economic Empowerment (EE), Social & Cultural Empowerment (SC), Leadership Empowerment (LED), and Economic Development (ED) all have a significant impact on Policy Support (PS), accounting for 72.6% of the variance. This moderate predictive power emphasizes how crucial it is to incorporate many aspects of empowerment in order to establish a conducive policy climate.

The reliability of regression findings is ensured by the near ideal Durbin-Watson value (Turner, 2020) i.e., around 2. This value verifies that there is no significant autocorrelation among residuals. The validity of the study's conclusions is further supported by the regression model's significance, which verified by the ANOVA test. The concepts themselves offer a thorough strategy for empowering women. For example, personal empowerment or PE, is essential in giving women the self-assurance and abilities they need to actively engage in the economy and society. In line with Vision 2030's goals to boost female employment participation, Economic Empowerment or EE focuses on integrating women in the workforce. The concept of Social and Cultural Empowerment or SC recognizes how cultural changes have helped women overcome historical obstacles and take on more important roles. Fostering female leaders who can impact policy and societal change is emphasized by Leadership Empowerment or LED. Though the model's predictive power indicates that there is potential for improvement, especially through the inclusion of additional factors or the adoption of robust statistical techniques in future research, these findings demonstrate the success of Vision 2030's objectives, which aim to empower women across social, economic and leadership domains.

VI. CONCLUSION

The outcomes of this research strongly support the central objective of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 – the

empowerment of women as a key driver of national progress. The analysis demonstrated that social, cultural, and leadership factors are deeply affixed with economic development, creating a synergistic framework that enhances womens participation across all spheres of life. The empirical evidence confirmed that policies fostering Personal, Economic, Social and Leadership Empowerment have a significant and positive impact on the advancement of women in Saudi Arabia. The ANOVA test and the validated regression model highlight the validity of these results and provide policymakers with useful information. Empowering women in Saudi Arabia is in line with the Vision 2030 and therefore priority should be given to programs that promote women leadership opportunities so had women can undertake significant roles in decision making roles across various industries. Women should be encouraged to enter the workforce and take up entrepreneurial activities as this is crucial in sustaining women empowerment across all sectors. Cultural initiatives that strengthens inclusivity should be promoted to foster an atmosphere in order to support women's active contribution in society. Furthermore legislative action go a long way in ensuring a society where women will play a positive role in the progress of Saudi Arabia as a nation. Going forward research in this area will require large sample size and more variables and further advance statistical tools to offer deeper insight related to the topic. In essence, this study not only affirms the achievements of Vision 2030 but also emphasizes that women's empowerment is integral to the Kingdom's social and economic transformation. Empowered women are catalysts for national development – strengthening families, enriching communities, and driving Saudi Arabia towards a more equitable and prosperous future.

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